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IRIS RECOGNITION TECHNOLOGY

Mrs.Meena Preethi.B, Priyanka.R, Christina Mercy.D

Department Of Software Systems
Sri Krishna Arts and Science College,
Kuniyamuthur, Coimbatore -641008, India

ABSTRACT:

This Biometric document is a “live” template. The various components of this paper contain iris recognition; working, features and application are already defined on this portrait, as illustrated by the portions given in this document.

Biometric is the process of authenticating a person in different forms as such facial expression, palm prints etc. Iris recognition is an example of biometric which identifies a person using their eye’s iris. Iris recognition software was developed by Daughman which was a securable device for the world. Iris recognition is unique and non intrusive

KEYWORDS: *Biometric recognition, iris positioning, image segmentation, iris recognition.*

INTRODUCTION:

Biometrics gets the interest and attraction of the world year by year. Biometric authentication refers and finds the uniqueness of person for identification .An input biometric authentic data is processed with the given identification for a match, which is of high recognition rate. Computer models includes the physical behavioral of human beings with a view of personal identification .It indeed the visual images and speech. Iris recognition is more accurate, intrusive. The iris which has inimitable iris pattern which is used for recognition, which works with the help of a camera. It’s a mathematical pattern identification technique .Scanning technology captures contrast image of the human eye’s iris, which have a constrain that it should have at least 3 to 10 inches from the device and after that the analyzing work starts.

HOW IT WORKS:

The Iris Access employs authentication without PIN numbers, passwords. For easy enrollment video based technology is used. This technology provides template for in cases of good life of the subject. Less than 2 seconds is needed for enrolling authentication. Scanning of iris is the common idea when we think of iris recognition technology, but there is no process of scanning in it.

Pattern recognition and pattern capturing is the main terminology on the basis of video camera technology, which has the property of a camcorder. Bright illumination or close-up imaging is not required for capturing. Enrollment Optional Unit commanded by audio assisted interactive interface, by a mirror to allow an auto focus camera for digital video of iris.

Using frame grabber individuals images from the live videos are captured. The pattern visible between the pupil and the sclera is analyzed for the process using innovative algorithm, which is converted into a code of 512 Byte digital template. Identification control unit with portals is the place where database and communication is kept for access privileges. Iris technology is also used for immigration processes in order to authenticate on the airport.

FEATURES:

Some of the innovative features of iris technique are:

- The grey scale image of the eye is read in 8 bit data
- A high degree of accuracy of auto detects eyelids, iris and pupil.
- The location of the iris and eyelids is manually specified inside the device.

IRIS RECOGNITION-TECHNOLOGY:

In Biometric technologies, we have many kinds like finger prints, palm prints, facial expression detection, iris recognition and voice recognition etc.. Iris recognition technology is more secure and comfortable when compared with many other Biometric technologies. It works with a camera and video in it, it offers dual or single eye capture within one or two seconds. It is not like other methodologies since, in finger printing technique many people have improper finger prints that are not suitable for recognition system but iris is an alternative for fingerprint because an individual will have his or her own unique iris pattern of them which will be registered in the scanner and it is well authenticated, Iris of even blind people can be accessed. This technology is suitable for all age groups.

In human body, Eyes are more fragile and protected, in which the size and pattern of the iris will not undergo much changes in the lifespan of human. Which is the favorable for a consistent biometric recognition technology. Algorithm of high-end professional which is Bioenable is used for iris recognition for high speed processing and matching. Its authenticating and securable technique is used in National ID, VISA entry application all through the universe.

Perhaps we can also make pattern recognition using matching solution based on Matlab. High resolution focused image of an Eye has been captured in the recognition technique. Further the captured Iris pattern is been sent to the statistical features for Biometric identification.

Is The Technology Reliable?

The technology is more authenticated and with a high security and its merit is proven to the world, for the application like passport control, airport and airline crew identification, in Olympics access control system. The Eye control technical crew have previously created many recognition technology which was not so effective. They have performed a million identification with zero errors using iris recognition software.

In passport control surveillance of immigration services of United Kingdom and Canada, now using Iris recognition technology. Its proven that top tier algorithm has high accuracy and spontaneous in identifying a person from a major record database by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST).

Proven As Amazing Technique Elsewhere:

Retinal scanning is an older Biometric technology maps the Blood vessel in the retina in the back of the Eye using light aimed. In Iris recognition technology, in contrast to retina identification it is outside and visible without invasive lighting at the back, it merely takes the Digital picture of the Eye and no Health information is given.

This technology was developed for a high volume of public and military national security application. Many information and studies on clinical identification were made for implementing in health care field. As a result, Patent-pending approaches and camera systems were developed for those needs, it is present at sensible cost for many applications.

Even though it is costlier than finger print and other technologies it is considered to be more reliable, accurate and high security providence for the user, it may cost USD200 onwards though full scale may cost USD2000.

ADVANTAGES:

- Methodology of uniqueness recognition of person iris identification is of High security
- Multi-lingual interface with touch screen is a major bane
- The user has larger database
- Dual Eye Iris capture camera, 10 inch spill proof touch screen, Enhanced graphical user interface are the working benefit of the iris attendance system.
- It store up to 10000 users (2 eyes each) and over 500000 logs

The important and reliable features of the software is, Advanced access control mechanism with Door sensors, Fire alarm, Multiple Door lock controls, Optional Face Recognition & Fingerprint recognition add-ons.

DISADVANTAGES:

- A lot of memory is stored for the data & it's very expensive.
- Small target (1 cm) is acquired for a 1m distance and the distance target within other changes.
- The position of the iris which is behind curved, wet, reflecting surfaces are not scanned accurately.
- Eyelashes, lenses, reflections will be an obstinate for the scanning process.
- The pupil varying size and drooping of eyelids is a non expanding demerit

APPLICATIONS:

- Hotel, canteen management like in food coupon systems.
- Visitors and members management in tourist events
- Membership and time attendance recording in offices
- Controls trespasser accessing and access controls in bank and other authenticated services.
- A classic biometric application is it secures the forensics acts and prevents bank accounts at cash machine, in birth certificates and helps in tracing wanted persons.

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